

**Press freedom in Yemen and its impact
on public opinion**

(Between 2009 and 2021)

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Introduction

The talk about press freedom in Yemen in the local and international circles took several dimensions, all of which indicate the deterioration of the levels of that freedom in light of the war in Yemen since 2015, although Yemeni journalists were encouraged by the outputs of the National Dialogue 2013, which restructured the press code of honor, in addition to some media laws that limited any media activity during the era of the late President Ali Abdullah Saleh.

According to the annual press freedom report of Reporters Without Borders, Yemen ranked 169th out of 179 countries, meaning that the ranking index indicates the bad situation of the press in Yemen, which the organization's reports indicate, in addition to the reports of the Yemeni Journalists Syndicate.

With regard to freedom of expression and opinion on a particular issue, this has been linked to the party from which the event originates, between those who are loyal to it and those who oppose it. For example, the Saudi series "Rashash" has caused popular discontent in Yemeni circles north and south, but at the media level, only the media in the north show that public opinion, simply because the north is even controlled by the Houthis, who are considered an outspoken opponent of Saudi Arabia.

On the other hand, the issue of the interruption of salaries for months for the employees of the government sector in northern Yemen was an issue of public opinion in the areas of legitimacy. From this point of view, public opinion was politicized according to the agenda of those in charge of the media.

The World Transparency Organization ranked Yemen 176 out of 180 countries in corruption indicators, which amounted to an attempt to undermine the freedom of journalists in various ways.

In this scientific paper, we will focus on press freedom during the last decade in which Yemen has witnessed several variables, the most prominent of which is the removal of Ali Abdullah Saleh from power, through the reformulation of contents related to press freedom, up to the situation of journalists in light of the 2015 war so far. The focus of public opinion will also be addressed to reconsider once again the reality of the military operations carried out by the Arab coalition in Yemen, and not resolve it so far. This issue was raised due to the spread of famine, the deterioration of prices and the UAE's military withdrawal from the coalition. This issue is common to all spectrums of the Yemeni people north and south, as reported by many newspapers, and used several means to enable public opinion to say this in light of the severe repression faced by journalists and citizens by the conflicting currents, according to the statistics of civil society organizations, as well as the Yemeni Journalists Syndicate.

Freedom of the press and media laws in Yemen

Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights stipulates that everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression, including the freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers (1).

International standards include the regulation of: the establishment of independent media bodies, diversity, the regulation of the work of media outlets and their affiliates, the right of access to information, and their civil and criminal restrictions.

Yemen was a signatory to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

If we come by comparison, the Universal Declaration guarantees the establishment of independent media outlets that are far from monopolizing power, and these means do not need to be licensed to establish them, and they can only be closed by a judicial ruling, based on a lawsuit filed in advance, and the subjection of all parties to trial sessions. However, on the contrary in Yemen, any media outlet must submit to power, from the moment of licensing, and its closure is often related to security decisions.

In terms of diversity, it is limited by the era of the late President Ali Abdullah Saleh. Most of the free media were not allowed to be established, but rather security prosecutions of every media outlet established without the permission of the authority, especially with the beginning of the wave of the southern movement in 2007, which was followed by the closure of the oldest southern Yemeni newspaper, Al-Ayyam, which broadcast public opinion issues in the southern regions.

President Saleh also retaliated against every journalist who opposed his policies, as happened with the editor-in-chief of the online newspaper Al-Mukalla Al-

Youm. Sanad Ba Yashout, when he was criticized in one of the press conferences held by President Saleh in Hadramout, where Ba Yashout criticized him for his treatment of the people that they do not have a wealth that establishes the infrastructure with which he is grateful to them, and he criticized them for years until Ba Yashout's car was bombed in 2014, and no one was harmed at the time, but the incident was terrifying and a message from the Saleh regime that Ba Yashout and his colleagues should stop directing their pens to the former regime¹.

These prosecutions ended with the removal of Ali Abdullah Saleh from power in 2011, as diversity began to take its course ideologically, religiously, politically and regionally. The Yemeni Journalists Syndicate monitored violations in 2009, the last year of safety for Saleh's systems, in which 153 cases of violation were recorded (2).

As for the regulation of the media and its employees in Yemen, which is one of the countries included in the Universal Declaration of Ethics for Journalists, it updated its press code of honor after the National Dialogue Conference 2013, which included the conditions of journalistic work, the rights and duties of journalists, the conditions of work of Arab and foreign journalists, the regulation of the activity of newspapers and magazines, the provisions related to printing presses, publishing houses, works and legal creativity, publication prohibitions and penal provisions, and the final general provisions.

The shift in press freedom after 2010

However, there is a press code of honor adopted by the Yemeni Journalists Syndicate during the seminar on the role of the media in creating the atmosphere of the National Dialogue Conference and supporting the democratic transition process in conjunction with the democratic transition witnessed by Yemen during

¹- Source: Al Ayyam, retrieved from <https://www.alayyam.info/news/5ZLXXFXU-T4U2MI>

the National Dialogue Conference 2013, where the charter came out with general principles (3):

Article (1) Commitment to support and make a success of the national dialogue and the democratization process

Article (2) Freedom within the Limitation of Obligation

Article (3) Professionalism within the Limitation of Liability

Article (4): In order to reflect the contents of this Charter on journalists and media professionals, the following:

1) Ensuring respect for the foundations on which the political settlement agreement was based, and the rules governing Yemen during the transitional period, including the Gulf Initiative and its implementation mechanism, and Security Council resolutions No. (2014, 2051).

2) Not to publish and broadcast any content that contradicts the principles of the noble Islamic religion, the objectives of the Yemeni revolution, the morals of society, traditions and social norms.

3) Avoiding any form of personal abuse of individuals and their privacy and freedoms .

4) Not to offend the national constants and social fabric of one Yemen.

5) Ensure that no form of discrimination is practiced between members of society on the basis of gender , color, sect, social class and profession.

These two charters come as a correction of the media system in force since 1990 when the two parts of Yemen united, where the press and publishing system, which is the only system that regulates the media process, was found by Republican Decree Law No. (25) of 1990, and we find it in the link below to the Yemeni Observatory for Human Rights, where it contains (166) Article (4).

There is no doubt that the government media system is repressive. It is a dual system between two mindsets that do not believe in media freedom. The first is a socialist mindset and the other is a monarchy in a republican dress.

As for the right of access to information, the fact that the media and the press in particular are a fourth authority, and more accurately a supervisory authority over the three powers (legislative – judicial – executive), the enjoyment of the right of access to information takes place amidst the extreme caution of journalists against revealing the sources of information, as well as endangering his life.

In light of this, Yemen is one of the six Arab countries that enacted laws guaranteeing the right to access information, after the removal of the Saleh regime, as the law was issued in 2012, and guarantees the right to access without delay, by the three authorities in the country, and any party funded from the state budget, and everyone has the right to access information, except for what affects the security of the state and its foreign policy (5).

However, with the length of that legal petition, the application remains the master of the scene, and it is missing. All the leaked documents of government agencies are made by employees who fear for themselves and cooperate with the Yemeni Journalists Syndicate.

The video report I reviewed on violations against journalists in Hadhramaut is a good witness to this.

The Yemeni Journalists Syndicate indicates that 112 cases of violations against journalists were monitored in 2020, as follows (6):

Infringing Entities	Number	Percentage	Violation Type
Hadi's	50	44.6%	One case of kidnapping and prosecution, 8 cases of threats and

government			incitement, 3 cases of summons, 2 cases of judicial investigation, and one case of assault on journalists' homes.
Houthi group	33	29.5%	10 cases of arrest, 9 cases of stalking and harassment, 7 cases of kidnapping, 5 cases of detention, and 2 cases of arrest.
National Transitional Council	12	10.7%	3 cases of torture, 6 cases of kidnapping and stalking,
Unknown Entities	13	11.6%	2 cases of physical liquidation, 7 cases of threats, 3 cases of assault on a media outlet, and 1 case of torture.
Advertising medium	3	2.7%	He didn't mention her.
A faction of the Resistance	1	0.9%	1 Threat Case
Total	122		

On World Press Day, May 3, the Yemeni Journalists Syndicate renewed the reminder of the tragedy of journalists, as cases of violation have increased since the last 2015 war to 1,400 violations, 44 deaths over ten years, and the severance of salaries of media workers, so that all efforts to promote press freedom go in vain after the end of the National Dialogue Conference, and all its provisions related to this are folded with it.

The Impact of the Yemeni Press on Public Opinion: The Revolution of the Hungry in (2021) as a Model

From time to time, Yemeni legitimacy is still supported by the Arab coalition led by Saudi Arabia calling for the liberation of Sana'a from the control of the Houthis, but the Yemeni, Gulf, and international community represented by the Security Council are talking about military intervention towards Sana'a, in an unprecedented difference with regard to what happened in Aden immediately after the announcement of Decisive Storm.

Amid questions about the conclusion of the battle, many developments emerged during 2021, which formed a public opinion in Yemen opposing the Arab coalition, accusing it of causing the suffering of Yemenis, as shown in publications that were recently linked to the emergence of what was known as the "hungry revolution" emerging in 2021.

The Yemeni press, both paper and electronic, has been able to shed light on many of the issues that Yemenis are going through, rather than the issue of controlling Sana'a, including:

- 1- The deterioration of currency exchange in southern Yemen and its repercussions on traders and citizens, causing a major humanitarian crisis and famine nationwide, as indicated by reports of international organizations.
- 2- Gulf reconciliation in Al Ula 2021, the UAE-Iran rapprochement 2019, and the Saudi-Iranian rapprochement 2021.
- 3- Political divisions in the circles of legitimacy before and after the Riyadh Agreement.
- 4- The reports of the Security Council experts in 2021, which accuses all parties of what the situation of Yemenis has become.

The highlighting of these issues in 2021 in the language of numbers – as followed by many media outlets, most notably: the economic newspaper "Bugsh", the newspaper "Aden al-Ghad", the TV channel "Balqis", the TV channel "Yemen Shabab", the channel "Al-Mahriya", and other media outlets of different political orientations – mobilized public opinion on social media demanding an end to the war in Yemen, which began last September with the "revolution of the hungry", during which a clash took place between the demonstrators and the security forces supported by the Arab Coalition, and these demonstrations began in Aden, Abyan, Hadramout, Shabwa, and Taiz.

While in Mahra and Socotra, the peaceful clash at times and the military at times against the Saudi and Emirati influence that is trying to control strategic interests in these two governorates.

More importantly, all media outlets through which journalists broadcast these issues are on social media, or opposition media outlets broadcasting from other countries such as Turkey and Egypt.

In social media, as a result of the above, many pages and groups calling for the revolution of the hungry were established in all Yemeni governorates, including:

- 1- The Hungry Revolution Movement: A Yemeni Facebook page, established in December 2020, followed by 20,300 people, publishes the news of the protests and their dates, and many pages were established in which the word hungry appears with the name of the region, for the purpose of organizing the protests²
- 2- The emergence of many hashtags on Facebook, Twitter and other engines during the month of September 2021, including: # The_Hungry_Revolution_Movement, # The_Hungry_Revolution and

²- Source: "Revolution of the Hungry" Facebook page, retrieved from the link: link: <https://www.facebook.com/thawrataljia/>

#The_People_are_dying. The published pictures also indicate the demand to end the military intervention of the Arab Coalition in Yemen, and to improve living conditions.

Analyzing public opinion (the revolution of the hungry) as a model

The start of the revolution of the hungry spontaneously and without sectarian or partisan support, indicates the success of the press, which played a role in shaping the orientation of public opinion towards the Yemeni crisis, taking advantage of social media.

Here we come to the American sociologist Herbert Plummer's saying that the term public is used to refer to a group of people:

A- They are faced with a specific "problem/issue" B- They are divided in their ideas about facing the problem C- They enter into a discussion about that issue

Bloomer considers that entering into the discussion on the issue is the reason for the existence of the public, as he defined it by saying: It is an unorganized group, whose size and membership change with the diversity of the issue, and instead of dictating its activities, it makes an effort to reach an action, and thus is forced to find its activity.

The issue of the "revolution of the hungry" is classified as a national rather than local public opinion, as it is at the level of a vast region that enjoys homogeneity, in addition to its predictability and dimensions through studies and measurements of public opinion research centers (7).

Through this issue, the Yemeni public opinion has also witnessed a shift in the quality of the influence and influence of what it hears and sees, from the guided or submissive opinion, to the educated (enlightened) opinion due to its friction with politics, because one of the characteristics of the coordinated opinion is that its members are affected by what is published and broadcast by the various media; as

they are unable to continue to see, search, and follow events, due to the low level of culture and education, and they do not have the ability to discuss issues as long as the leaders have portrayed to them that these problems affect their interests, and this was already at the beginning of the military operations in Yemen when the Yemeni press portrayed the danger of the Houthis on the doctrine of the Yemenis, and the future of Yemen under their rule, and that the Yemen war is ideological.

In the rise of educated (enlightened) opinion, more groups were formed than the active group – that is, the group that dominates public opinion – and researchers call this group the conscious public, as Devine set for it exploratory measures to determine the conscious public that revolves around its interest in politics and reading its news.

He supports the vision of Devine James Price, who believes that public opinion is formed when it moves from the stage of negative public opinion to the active conscious public opinion that not only prevails, but governs as well.

Recommendations

- 1- Relying on secure VPN programs in the press messaging process so that those hostile to press freedom do not follow the press editors, especially in light of the Houthis' control of the Communications Control Center in Sana'a, and the coalition's control of the Communications Control Center in Aden.
- 2- Encouraging citizen journalism, which is now reporting the facts from the Yemeni governorates, through virtual communication with them in the social media in which they are active, and the journalist's commitment to hiding sources of information in order to preserve the lives of others from tracking down the concerned authorities, and the need to encourage citizen journalism as an alternative to the press representative who is threatened by violations against them.
- 3- The formation of human rights committees in cooperation between the Yemeni Journalists Syndicate and local and international bodies to prosecute figures who violated the freedom of journalists, based on the principle of "the right does not fall under the statute of limitations", especially since at the present time the Syndicate has not risen to the level of human rights coordination in order to ensure that journalists whose rights have been violated are taken into account.
- 4- Activating the constitutional provisions emanating from the transitional period that Yemen went through between 2011 and 2013, which stipulate the right to access information, and that the state guarantees the right of all spectra to freedom of expression, because these constitutional provisions were not applied due to the events in Yemen in 2015.
- 5- Creating a press code of honor that differs from the previous press charters in Yemen, as it includes that the press is the eye of society on what is

happening with a commitment to transparency and credibility, and society is the protector of it in light of the political division that the country is witnessing, and the evidence of the effectiveness of this type of charter is the solidarity that Yemeni citizens have made towards the case of the four journalists against whom the Houthis issued the death sentence, as well as the case of the journalists Abdullah Bakir and Ahmed Al-Yazidi, who were arbitrarily arrested by the second military region of the Hadi government, and the criminal court was unable to issue any judgment condemning them for an act contrary to the law, as solidarity was the emergence of marches of citizens demanding an end to violations against them, as well as their interaction through social media platforms.

References

United Nations (n.d.). *Universal Declaration of Human Rights* (UDHR)

Retrieved from link:

<https://www.un.org/ar/universal-declaration-human-rights/index.html>

2) Yemeni Journalists Syndicate. (2009). *Violations suffered by journalists during 2009*. Retrieved from link:

<https://www.yemenjs.net/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/pdf.pdf>

3) The National Information Center of the Presidency of the Republic of Yemen. (2013, March 14). *The text of the Charter of Political and Media Honor, adopted at the seminar on the role of the media in creating the atmosphere of the National Dialogue Conference*. Retrieved from link:

https://yemen-nic.info/national_dialogue/trans/news/detail.php?ID=53659&print=Y

4) The National Information Center of the Presidency of the Republic of Yemen. (n.d.). *Press and Publications Act 1990*. Retrieved from link:

https://yemen-nic.info/db/laws_je/detail.php?ID=6716

5) Public Prosecution of Yemen. (2012). *Enforcement of the Right to Information Act* Retrieved from link:

http://agoyemen.net/lib_details.php?id=195

6) Yemeni Journalists Syndicate. (2021, Jan 6). *Annual report on press freedom during the year 2020*. Retrieved from link:

<https://www.yemenjs.net/?p=698>

7) The slave, Atef. (2006). *Public opinion and ways of measuring it*. (First Edition, p. 21 – p. 22 – p. 26) Cairo, Egypt: Dar Al-Fikr Al-Arabi.